
MANAGEMENT DEVELOPMENT AND EMPLOYEE EFFECTIVENESS OF OIL FIRMS IN NIGER DELTA, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Management development is a process that creates effective managers, which enable managers to acquire skills and learn to recognize behaviours, builds confident and effectiveness. This study investigated management development and employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria. The study focus on the impact of: learning-through-work on employee effectiveness; impact of formal training on employee effectiveness; impact of feedback on employee effectiveness; of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria. Five (5) research questions and five null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. related literature were reviewed. The study was anchored on learning theory, social exchange theory and resource-based theories which provide a theoretical background to the study. The study adopted survey design with a population of 410 employees and a sample size of 201. Questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. Descriptive (percentage, mean and standard deviation) and inferential (multiple regressions) statistics were used to analyze collected data. The findings of the study revealed that: there is a significant impact of learning-through-work on employee effectiveness (0.000); there is a significant impact of formal training on employee effectiveness (0.001) and there is a significant impact of feedback on employee effectiveness (0.005) on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria. It was concluded that management development enhances communications skill; adaptability, flexibility, builds strong culture, gives high moral and ability to adapt to change. It was recommended among others that organisations should create environment where learning is as instinctive as breathing, to unlock the full potential of a workforce.

Keywords:

Management development, Employee effectiveness, Learning-through-work, Formal training, Feedback.

INTRODUCTION

Management is process of supervising, conducting, and directing employees. Modern work environment depends on the strength of those in managerial positions, to organise, direct, coordinate and supervise organisational resources to achieve set goals. Herrity (2024) defined management “coordination” and “administration” of tasks. Administration involves strategies and coordinating employees’ efforts to accomplish their responsibilities using available resources. Supporting this, Mathur (2024) reveals, “Management can be defined as all the activities and tasks undertaken for archiving goals by continuous activities like; planning, organizing, leading and controlling.” Bondarouk and Parry (2021) ascertain that management is an art and science of getting work done through people. Malsam (2023) revealed that managers are individuals who possess skills such as “planning, communication, organization and leadership”, to implement managerial activities for achieving organisational goal.

Management development enables manager to acquire skills and learn to recognize behaviours builds confident and effectiveness. Ahmad (2023) view management development as a process that creates effective managers. Employee, who facilitates people to do their job for the purpose of achieving organisational goal, is a manager. Management development programmes enable managers to enhance their existing skills, resolve conflicts and communicate with others. Alagah (2022) identify internal and external management development programmes; a firm might provide individual mentorship, instruction from a human resources department representative for new or experienced managers to complete on-site via the implementation of internal management development programme. While organisations implement external management development programme via conferences, seminars or even university graduate programmes. Some key principles of management development include knowledge, skills and abilities development. Ramesh (2017) argued that the basic approaches to management development are: learning through work, formal training, feedback, facilitation and support, which can be achieved through both formal and informal means.

The significance of management development cannot be over emphasis; without, organisations can not be successful because it helps those new employees to understand what the job entails, gain necessary skills and knowledge. Ali and Mehreen (2019) opined that, the benefits of management development include, (1) Effective organisation: Management development can help new and existing managers learn better ways to connect with their coworkers and report to their supervisors; (2) Motivate team members - this process can make managers more effective; (3) Cost efficient leadership - it can save itself the cost of hiring and training new managers; (4) Increase knowledge of organisation’s policies: it can keep everyone updated on firm’s expectations, culture and policies; and (5) Long-term management availability: It can ensure knowledgeable and effective managers in the long term. Management development helps organizations to grow managers to meet present and future needs. It improves managers’ performance, gives them development opportunities, and provides for management succession. Sartika and Aqsa (2022) revealed, “Management development enables managers to understand what is expected of them; align with organisation’s objectives and acquire competence skills in respect to their responsibilities; improve the performance, identify managers with potential, encourage managers to prepare and implement personal development plans.

Employee effectiveness is how-well employee can do a job to acquired desirable result. It is the degree of employee’ performance under ideal and controlled circumstances; the way employees carry out their responsibility to produce a desired and effective result. Burches and Burches

(2024) reported, “Employee effectiveness is doing things in the most economical way”. The extent to which employees believe in themselves plays a significant role in performing new tasks, learning, productivity to mention but a few. Mingyue, Krampah-Nkoom, Manu and Oduro (2022) opine that employee effectiveness is employee’s belief in his/her capacity to execute behaviors necessary to produce specific performance attainments.

Effectiveness reflects in an employee’s belief to get things done, feel motivated to positively impact performance. It is a crucial mindset that ties directly to quality of work at an individual level. Carter, Nesbit, Badham, et al. (2018), employee effectiveness can lower anxiety and help people better cope with stress. This is a crucial mindset that improve employees’ level of effectiveness. Management development, role models and recognition can increase employee efficacy (Arciniega, Servitje, & Woehr, 2021).

Oil firms are businesses who are into “exploration”, “production”, “refine”, “sell and/or distribution oil and gas”. Most of their activities and assets include “exploration and drilling, transportation via trucks, tankers, pipelines, refineries, and gas stations” to mention but a few (Chen, 2022). Oil firms that strive for success improve employees’ effectiveness to enhance ease achievement of organisations’ goals. To this end, management development plays a significant role. Oil firms need to develop programme that will enhance their employees. The goal of management development programme is to improve employees’ effectiveness; organisations can possess a base of potentials, already made employees who are waiting for opportunities to explore (Tujuba, 2022). Oil firms are essential to “Nigerian economy, managers, stakeholders, operators, practitioners/stakeholders, therefore it is inevitable to do without the implementation of management development in oil firms. Thus, oil firms should develop their employees by providing employees with the necessary skills, knowledge and ability to do their job effective under the guide of their organisations.

One of the greatest ways to grow and develop effective/high-quality leaders is by implementing management development programmes. Many firms face shortage of employees and high turnover rates because they fail to understand the importance of internal recruitment and promotion. Thus, organisation should focus on training programme to find employees’ untapped talent, provide the skills, knowledge, and experience to become a great leader. This will help organisation leadership role via created talent base that is ready and waiting for opportunity to explore. It will also to improve in experienced managers. Base on the aforementioned, this study examined management development and employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria.

The study therefore ascertain management development and Employee Effectiveness of oil Firms in the Niger Delta, Nigeria. Specific objectives of the study are to determine the impact of:

- i. learning-through-work on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria;
- ii. formal training on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria;
- iii. feedback on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Management Development

Management development is the process of developing skills and competencies to perform in management positions; by existing or new managers (Damanik, Lumbanraja and Sinulingga, 2020). It may also be referred to as leadership development or executive education. Karina and Ardana (2020) argued that, “management development is a continuous, systematic process that helps employees reach their full potential by building strengths, managing weaknesses, and exploring career development opportunities”. Bajaj, R., & Sharma ascertain that management development has several forms which include: (1) formal management development program offered by universities, colleges, or private training providers to train managers from scratch, (2) In-house management development program developed by organisations, and (3) Informal learning experiences that occur on the job, such as through mentoring relationships with more experienced managers.

Management development attempts to increase managers' performance in their current duties while also preparing them for future responsibilities. Akhigbemidu et al. (2021) define it as a learning-based endeavor to improve managerial performance. It's a methodical approach to influencing someone's knowledge or abilities. Management development and talent management are intertwined. A deliberate way to deal with the board advancement is fundamental because of the expanding obligations put on line supervisors. Line administrators are currently needed to have a bigger scope of created abilities than any time in recent memory. Performance management, development centers, personal development planning, coaching, and mentoring are all part of the organization's approach to help employees. Although management development intercessions, for example, those outlined above are necessary, a strict, organization-wide program is not required (Akhigbemidu et al., 2021).

One of the most essential components in every organization's success is the growth of her management team. This is since managers must be able to balance their technical understanding, social competence, and conceptual knowledge and abilities, all of which are absorbed via a fusion of education and knowledge (Ahmad (2023). Preparing a manager for anticipated changes in their career or a future position is usually seen as management development. Managerial training is often regarded as a critical component of an organization's growth and development. Whatever the case may be, management training is as important for public sector organizations as it is for private ones. For Gold, Thorpe, and Mumford, it was clear that programs developed by the company for improvement don't simply happen; it requires planning, which was always essential for any business, but also the tasks of building up a human workforce. It also includes the design and upgrading of jobs, which includes collecting and organizing them. To help people grow and succeed in the workplace, this is tailored to the company's needs; upgrading and altering employments make employees and assignments fit together as best they can. In addition, the frameworks of control plan pave the way for people to make informed decisions. Management development creates an empowered workforce that is capable of coping with changes and complexity because of experience learning and ongoing management training.

A systematic approach to management development is necessary because the increasingly onerous demands made on line managers mean that they require a wider range of developed skills than ever before. Managers need the ability to: empower and develop people – understand

and practise the process of delivering through the capability of others; manage people and performance – managers increasingly need to maintain morale whilst also maximizing performance; work across boundaries, engaging with others, working as a member of a team, thinking differently about problems and their solutions; develop relationships and a focus on the customer, building partnerships with both internal and external customers; balance technical and generic skills – the technical aspects of management and the management of human relationships.

There are number of priorities for management development. These are: combining a strong corporate architecture for management development with a capability for ‘just in time’ and local delivery to meet specific business needs; providing better information and advice for individual managers on how to think about their future direction in career terms and their learning needs; mainstreaming the skills required to manage self-development and to support the development of others; these skills include those of ‘manager as coach’ but also go wider and include informal career mentoring; finding ways of delivering more stretching and stimulating management development to the whole population of managers, not just those in very senior posts or identified as ‘high potential’ (Alagah, 2022).

Learning-Through-Work

Learning through work is experiential learning, learning through action, learning by doing, learning through experience, and learning through discovery and exploration, is a popular approach that “erases the boundaries that separate learners from the knowledge they need”. Nyamori (2020), opines that learning through work has several benefits to workplace, such as “developing communications skills, professional development, teamwork, making onboarding more efficient, and building a stronger company culture”. It enables managers to look for a new way of doing job, carry out responsibilities and successfully articulate views. Learning-through-work stakeholders have the power and responsibility to speak up for themselves. When it comes to a certain movement, it's not what employee do that offers an experience, but how it is been done So, how are experiential learning activities created? The following might serve as a basic framework (Muhammad, Nadeem & Huzaifah, 2022).

It is a powerful form of learning. It involves what can be done for managers to make the best use of their experience. It is an experiential learning that comes naturally to some managers; they seem to absorb, unconsciously and by some process of osmosis, the lessons from their experience, the capability to develop instantaneous analysis, which is stored in their mental databank, can be retrieved whenever necessary (Niati, Siregar, & Prayoga, 2021). This makes use of the learning experiences that managers meet during the course of their everyday work. Managers learn from daily problem encountered and evolve new ways of dealing with the situation. They learn to analyse what they do, how and why it contributed to success or failure. This retrospective or reflective learning is effective base on its future application. (Guan & Frenkel, 2019).

It has often been said that managers learn to manage by managing – in other words, ‘experience is the best teacher’. This is largely true, but some people learn much better than others (Al-Rawahi, 2022). After all, a manager with 10 years’ experience may have had no more than one year’s experience repeated 10 times. Differences in the ability to learn arise because some managers are naturally more capable or more highly motivated than others, while some will have had the benefit of the guidance and help of an effective boss who is fully aware of his or

her responsibilities for developing managers. This type of ‘experiential’ learning comes naturally to some managers. They seem to absorb, unconsciously and by some process of osmosis, the lessons from their experience, although in fact they they have probably developed a capacity for almost instantaneous analysis, which they store in their mental databank and which they can retrieve whenever necessary (Bajaj & Sharma, 2018).

There are numerous benefits of learning at work. These benefits include: opportunities to up skill staff is a win-win for both employees and organisations; employees can grow and develop skills; organisation can identify reliable and competent employees who can deliver at all levels; employees feel supported, valued, and motivated; great Employee Retention; employees become more flexible and adaptable; encourages the development of soft skills; enhance clear career progression; increased employee effectiveness, efficacy and new methods of doing things. In General, it develops employees, grow their skill sets and become valuable assets. An individual will capabilities, confident and proactively plan work strategies which business can harness and use to great advantage (Huang, P., & Yao, 2017). Learning helps prepare employees to handle their job effectively. It gives opportunities to understand whether employees’ chosen career is right (Nabunya, Mukwenda, & Kyaligonza, 2019).

Formal Training

The formal approaches to management development are based on the identification of development needs through performance management or a development centre. It is structured on a list of generic or core competences; which have been defined as being appropriate for managers. Formal approaches include: (1) development on the job through coaching, counselling, monitoring and feedback by managers on a continuous basis associated with the use of performance management processes to identify and satisfy development needs, and with mentoring; (2) development through work experience, which includes job rotation and enlargement, taking part in project teams or task groups, ‘action learning’, and secondment outside the organization; (3) formal training by means of internal or external courses – although management training programmes are more likely to be delivered in a series of modules over a number of months rather than a single, long, residential course; (4) structured self-development by following self-managed learning programmes agreed as a personal development plan or learning contract with the manager or a management development adviser – these may include guidance reading or the deliberate extension of knowledge or acquisition of new skills on the job; (5) e-learning (AL-Rawahi, 2022; Niati et al., 2021).

According to Alagah (2022), management training is intended to encourage realizing so that individuals can become more successful at completing parts of their work, recognizing that it is teacher-driven and content-based mediation prompting desired changes in conduct and that it, except for hands-on management training, includes time away from the workplace. To put it another way, it's an exercise in growth and development. A key part of management training is accelerating individual and hierarchical learning with other less orderly activities including teaching, tutoring, and peer group learning (Alagah, 2022).

Formal training improves knowledge, skills and change employees’ attitudes. It poses several benefits for employers and employees. Amada et al. (2021) reported the following as benefits of training: (a) High Morale: Training not only improves the basic skill and knowledge of employees but also moulds their attitudes towards organization's activities and generates greater

loyalty; (b) Higher Productivity: Training provides opportunities to learn technical know-how; (c) Quick Learning: A well planned and systematic training program provides opportunity for trainee for quick learning. d) Better Management: Training programmes are used to manage organizational activities. It facilitates overall management functions by providing efficient and capable human resource. Abdulmalek et al. (2024) identify reasons for training as: (1) capital improvement: employees are asset to the organization but employers are more concerned about reaching deadlines and profit maximization rather than employees skills development; (2) morale improvement and (3) ability to adapt to change

Training programs that assist employees to focus on their strengths and abilities help company to achieve both short-term and long-term goals. When it comes to the structure of management, employees' interest is taken into account. The more employees are allowed to involve in managerial activities, the more motivated they are. Fletcher et al. (2018) ascertained that training encourage employees to be successful at work. The key role of management training is accelerating individual and hierarchical learning which include teaching, tutoring, and peer group learning. Training is a solution to problems; it reduces involuntary employees' turnover and provides a means of preventing skills obsolescence. Training increases organisation's profitability and employees' effectiveness (Suma & Budi, 2021). Training enhances employee's personal qualities that increase performance to influences bottom line, saves cost and reduce employee turnover (Ahmad, 2023).

Feedback

Feedback is a significant component, "designed to help identify employees' strengths and weaknesses at workplace". It improves work done; builds positive comments and using the critical ones to inform changes at workplace. It is immediate and future-focused; it is more relevant when shared by a manager and more actionable when received by an employee. Relevant and continuous feedback means team members will know, where they are going wrong, and how good their performance is (Mensah, et al., 2017). This can stimulate a powerful positive shift in company's corporate culture. Via open communication and frequent feedback, managers make better use of goal-setting frameworks to set relevant goals that motivate employees and align with corporate objectives.

Feedback reveals level of employee's performance. Through feedback, "employee gain valuable insights that refine their performance and enhance organisational performance (Alison, 2020; Nabunya, Mukwenda, & Kyaligonza, 2019). It also helps employee to deeply consider their performance, identify areas of growth, and build upon their strengths which in turn increase organisational performance" (Huang & Yao, 2017; Janes, 2018). Feedback and constructive criticism improve results. Feedback might abuse an individual, especially if it's delivered insensitively or disrespectfully. It is an element of learning and assessment; which improve learning; assists employee to reflect on performance for necessary adjustments (Muhammad, Nadeem & Huzaiifah, 2022).

The importance of feedback include: "(1) keeping goals aligned across the organization (2) letting employees know what they are doing well (3) improving employee performance and (4) providing ongoing motivation". As a tool for continuous training, feedback helps employees gain insight into one's development by examining development experiences. Feedback reviews form an important and integral part of your professional development plan (Nyamori, 2020).

Feedback enables employees to receive information their practice, analyze their instructional approaches, and make informed adjustments.

Employee Effectiveness

Effectiveness is the degree of work done. Therefore, employee effectiveness is a how well a required result is produced by employee using available resources. Organisation's effectiveness is the combination of individual employee effectiveness; it is a "proportion of how well a firm's resources are used for achieving a lot of results achieving the most elevated amount of performance with minimal consumption of resources, including HR". Employee effectiveness includes estimating the time spent in the creation of a desire result. Alagah (2022) sees employee effectiveness as the extent of the time required for an employee to get work done within a set-standard time to the amount and nature of work done, while putting into thought the expense of the resources brought about. He further characterized employees' efficiency as a proportion of the general productivity, adequacy, and performance of an individual firm.

Effectiveness is seen as the extent of the time required to complete an obligation within a set-standard time to the amount and nature of work done, while putting into thought the expense of the resources brought about (Na-Nan & Sanamthong, 2020)). Mohamud (2014) characterized workers' efficiency as a proportion of the general productivity, adequacy, and performance of an individual firm. Mohamud (2014) argues that employee efficiency is the "proportion of how well a firm's resources are used for achieving a lot of results achieving the most elevated amount of performance with minimal consumption of resources, including HR". Employee effectiveness is a disposition of the psyche. It is the mindset of advancement and steady improvement of that which exists. It is the conviction of having the capacity to change what exists. It is the conviction of having the capacity to improve today than yesterday. It is the will to enhance the current circumstance, regardless of how great it might look. It is the proceeded with exertion to apply new strategies and it is the confidence in human abilities. Employees are concerned about the last and explicit yields wanted from the worker considering the resources spent on the worker (Mohamud, 2014). Employee efficiency includes estimating the time spent in the creation of the ideal yields from a worker. The worker includes additionally the estimation of the worker-related expenses brought about by the firm in the creation of wanted yield (Alagah, 2022).

Employee effectiveness is a procedure by which firms adjust their resources, frameworks, and workers' schedule to meet vital goals and needs. It is a precise procedure by which the general performance of an organization can be upgraded by improving the performance of people inside a group system. Workers' efficiency the managers goes for advancing extraordinary performance by conveying management desires, characterizing every worker's job inside a required capability system, and setting up benchmarks. Employee effectiveness includes meeting the objectives and goals for the team, or other recognized groups, some type of performance survey and following to diagram advancement and record accomplishment are key stages prompting thorough performance and improvement designs; as Alagah (2020) takes into account that employee efficiency to include worker's advancement with result based appraisal, it includes analysis, target setting, timely learning plans, and performance-related pay. As previously noted, it tends to be construed that employee efficiency involves all organization activities for starting and following a performance of an organization through its employees. In this manner, the motivation behind employee efficiency is to improve performance by meeting targets, and objectives.

Conceptual Framework

Independent Variables

Researcher's Conceptualisation (2024)

Fig. 1: Conceptual Model of the Study

Fig. 1 shows that learning-through-Work, Formal Training and Feedback have significant impacts on employee effectiveness (dependent variable). These impacts are beneficiary to both employers and employees. It improves employee effectiveness, develop skills, develop knowledge, develop ability, recognize behaviors, accomplishments, builds confident and effectiveness.

Theoretical Review

Learning Theory

Learning theory was propounded by John B. Watson and Schunk (1991), who described "learning" as, a long-term change in an individual's behavior as the result of practice. A long-term shift in behavior is an effect of practice. Vygotsky (1978) categorizes learning theories into three main categories: (a) Behaviourism, which is a philosophy of animal and human learning that focuses on objectively observable behaviors and disregards mental activities; (b) Constructivism, which is a philosophy of human and non-human learning; and (c) the brain's structure and function are the foundations of the cognitive learning theory. Learning will occur if the brain is not prevented from doing its usual functions, according to this theory. It is based on the idea that through reflecting on our experiences, one constructs and depicts their concept of the world they live in, which they use to draw/give meaning to their experiences. As a result, learning is a continuous process of adjusting one's mental models to take into account new information. Bruner (1960) made a famous observation about epistemological viewpoints that serve as a basis for several theoretical philosophies, in keeping with the explanations provided above. Psychologists in the field of social psychology appear to believe that the mind receives information in a variety of ways.

Learning theory describes how individual receive, process, and retain knowledge during learning. Cognitive, emotional, and environmental influences, as well as prior experience, all play a part in how understanding, or a worldview, is acquired or changed and knowledge and skills retained (Willingham, 2015). Behaviorists look at learning as an aspect

of conditioning and advocating a system of rewards and targets in education. Educators who embrace cognitive theory believe that the definition of learning as a change in behaviour is too narrow, and study the learner rather than their environment and in particular the complexities of human memory. Those who advocate constructivism believe that a learner's ability to learn relies largely on what they already know and understand, and the acquisition of knowledge should be an individually tailored process of construction. Transformative learning theory focuses on the often-necessary change required in a learner's preconceptions and worldview. Geographical learning theory focuses on the ways that contexts and environments shape the learning process.

The theory of multiple intelligences, where learning is seen as the interaction between dozens of different functional areas in the brain each with their own individual strengths and weaknesses in any particular human learner, has also been proposed, but empirical research has found the theory to be unsupported by evidence. Other learning theories have also been developed for more specific purposes. For example, andragogy is the art and science to help adults learn. Connectivism is a recent theory of networked learning, which focuses on learning as making connections. The Learning as a Network (LaaN) theory builds upon connectivism, complexity theory, and double-loop learning. It starts from the learner and views learning as the continuous creation of a personal knowledge network (PKN) (Cormier & Hagman, 2014).

2.3 Empirical Review

Abdulmalek, Naelati, Suryo and Eko (2024) studied, “The factors that influence employee performance within business contexts”. Their sample size was 135 employees with a total of 360 employees of Al-Saeed Company. Questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. Data was analysed using the PLS software. The study reveals that, “development and training, work-life quality, safety, and job satisfaction do not affect employee performance, while effectiveness positively influences employee performance”.

Widjaja (2023) examined, “The effectiveness of employee management strategies during organizational transformation, focusing on their impact on agility, resilience, and success”. The study used qualitative approach to analysed literature. Data collection was done via journals, books, and reputable online sources. The findings show that, “Agile performance management, characterized by flexibility and continuous feedback, is identified as crucial for adaptability and it was suggested that organizations need to implement comprehensive employee management strategies that resonate with their strategic goals to navigate transformation effectively”.

Alagah (2022) examined, “The stimulating influence of management development on workers' efficiency of the insurance industry in Rivers State”. The population size of 62 and a sample size of 56 respondents; correctional research design was adopted. The outcome of the analysis is, experiential learning, management training, and technology has significant effects on workers' efficiency. The Spearman' Rank Order Correlation Coefficient was used via the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences. The researcher recommended that, “experiential learning should be encouraged as it gives room for critical thinking, enhances problem solving and increases decision making skills”.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive research design which describes the characteristics of a population or phenomenon being studied. This research design helps researcher to identify, observed and measure characteristics in a study area to guide decisions and help answer questions in respect to the research problem” (Mills, 2024) .

The population of the study consisted of employees at management level of selected Oil firms from four states in the Niger-Delta, Nigeria. The four states (Delta, Akwa-Ibom, Rivers and Imo) was selected using convenience sampling techniques, thereafter, the following firms were randomly selected using the simple random sampling technique: Agip, Warri, Delta State (85); Exxon-Mobil, Uyo, Akwa-Ibom State (115); Shell Petroleum, Port-Harcourt, Rivers State (132) and Saplat Energy Service, Owerri, Imo State (78), with a population of 410 employees.

The study adopted a sample size was 201, derived from the total population of 410 using Krejcie and Morgan Sample Size Calculation Table. Krejcie and Morgan Table is used when a researcher do not have access to the entire statistical population of interest and need make decision based on representative sample (Syed, 2021). The 201 respondents will be chosen from the four selected oil firms located in the Niger Delta (Appendix B), Nigeria, based on proportionate sampling technique using the formula below:

$$\frac{PU}{PS} \times S$$

$$1$$

Where;

PS = Population of the Study = 410

PU = Population of a particular Oil firm

S = Sample Size = 201

This study adopted multi-stage sampling technique. First, convenience sampling techniques was used to pick four states in Niger Delta, Nigeria namely: Delta State, Akwa-Ibom State, Rivers State and Imo State. Secondly, a random sampling technique was used to select one Oil firms from each of the above mentioned states namely: Agip, Warri, Delta State; Exxon-Mobil, Uyo, Akwa-Ibom State; Shell Petroleum, Port-Harcourt, Rivers State and Saplat Energy Service, Owerri, Imo State. Thirdly, based on availability, the employees that are on sit (present) were chosen from each of the above mentioned oil firms proportionately to distribute the sample size of 201 according to the proportion of the population in each of the selected oil firms in the Niger Delta, to the total population of the study.

The instrument adopted for data collection was questionnaire which was designed based on a 5-point Likert scale of Strongly Agree (SA) Agree (A), Undecided (U) Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD), where: SA = 5, A = 4, U = 3, D = 2 AND SD = 1

The researcher administered 201 copies of questionnaires to the respondents after due permission from the managers of the selected Oil firms in the Niger Delta of Nigeria. This was done after explaining the purpose of the exercise to the respondents and establishing a rapport. Out of the 201 copies of questionnaire distributed to the respondents, 200 copies were retrieved and used for data analysis which show 99.5% retrieval rate.

Collected data from the administration of questionnaire was analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Descriptive statistic: means (x) and simple percentage were used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using multiple regressions via SPSS 25 at a significant level of 0.05.

The model of multiple regressions as follow:

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 \dots\dots\dots + \beta_nX_n$$

$$EE = \beta_0 + \beta_1LW + \beta_2FT+ \beta_3FB$$

Where:

EF = Employee Effectiveness = Dependent Variable

LW = Learning Through Work

FT = Formal Training

FB = Feedback

β_0 = the value of BP when all the independent variables

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ = the estimated regression coefficients.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Data Analysis of Demographical Data of Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	108	54
	Female	92	46
Years	Below 35	40	15
	35-50	36	18
	51-60	60	30
	Above 60	24	40
Educational Background	SSCE	22	11
	NCE/OND	66	33
	HND/BSC	82	41
	M.Sc./Ph.D	30	15

Source: Field survey, 2025

In Table 1. In gender distribution, 108 of the respondents which represent 54% were males while 92 of the respondents which represent 46% were females. 36 respondents which represent 18% were below 35 years; 60 respondents which represent 30% were between the age brackets of 35-50 years; 80 respondents which represent 40% were between 51-60 years while 24 respondents which represent 12% were above 60 years. 22(11%) of the total respondents were SSCE holder; 66 (33%) respondents were NCE/OND holder; 82(41%) of the total respondents were HND/B.Sc. holder while 30(15%) of the total respondents were M.Sc./Ph.D holder.

Pearson Correlation Matrix

Table 2: Pearson Correlation Result

	EE	LW	FT	FB
EE	1	.889	.918	.866
LW	.889	1	.780	.932
FT	.918	.780	1	.766
FB	.866	.932	.766	1

Source: Field Survey (2024)

Table 2 shows the Pearson correlation of management development and employee effectiveness. The result showed that all the coefficients of the variables: LW($r=0.889$), FT($r=0.918$) and FB($r=0.866$) This indicates that there is positive relationship between the variables.

Test of Hypotheses

Multiple regression analysis was used to test the hypotheses of this study in order to determine the relationship between variables. The analysis was done using SPSS 25 and the output was interpreted accordingly.

$$EE = \beta_0 + \beta_1LW + \beta_2FT+ \beta_3FB$$

Where:

EE = Employee Effectiveness = Dependent Variable

LW = Learning Through Work

FT = Formal Training

FB = Feedback

OUTPUT OF REGRESSION ANALYSIS IN SPSS 25

Table 3: Model Summary

	r	r ²	Adjusted r ²	Std. Error	Durbin-Watson
	0.961	0.923	0.921	0.08753	0.367

The r value of 0.961 (Table 3) shows the degree of relationship between the variables. This implies that there is a strong and positive correlation across the variables since the value of r (0.961) tends to 1. The r₂ value of 0.92 indicated that 92% of variation in employee effectiveness can be explained by the independent variables (LW, FT and FB).

Table 4: Anova

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Regression	17.772	5	3.554	463.896	0.000
	Residual	1.486	194	.008		
	Total	19.259	199			

The value of Sig (0.00) in Table 4.8 indicates that, the independent variables (FA, LW and FB) combined, have a statistically significant association with the employee effectiveness (EE).

Table 5: Coefficients

		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	0.858	0.117		7.323	0.000		
	LW	0.381	0.073	0.435	5.197	0.000	0.057	17.613
	FT	0.368	0.026	0.623	14.410	0.001	0.213	4.692
	FB	0.108	0.038	0.198	2.832	0.005	0.082	12.223

a. Dependent Variable: EF

Table 4.6 show the individual sign-value which indicates whether or not each of the independent variables has a statistically significant relationship with the dependent variable.

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant impact of learning-through-work on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria.

In Table 5, the sign-value of LW (0.000) implies that, learning-through-work has a significant relationship with employee effectiveness; since $0.000 < 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant impact of learning-through-work on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria is rejected. This implies that, there is a significant impact of learning-through-work on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria.

Therefore, forever additional effort of improving learning-through-work, employee effectiveness is expected to increase by coefficient of 0.381 (Table 5) assuming other independent variables remain constant.

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant impact of formal training on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria.

In Table 5, the sign-value of FT (0.001) implies that, formal training has a significant relationship with employee effectiveness; since $0.001 < 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant impact of formal training on employee effectiveness of Oil

Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria is rejected. This implies that, there is a significant impact of formal training on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria.

Therefore, forever additional effort of improving formal training, employee effectiveness is expected to increase by coefficient of 0.368 (Table 5) assuming other independent variables remain constant.

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant impact of feedback on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria.

In Table 5, the sign-value of FB (0.005) implies that, feedback has a significant relationship with employee effectiveness; since $0.005 < 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis which stated that, there is no significant impact of feedback on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria is rejected. This implies that, there is a significant impact of feedback on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria.

Therefore, forever additional effort of improving feedback, employee effectiveness is expected to increase by coefficient of 0.108 (Table 5) assuming other independent variables remain constant.

Discussion of Findings

The test of hypothesis 1 revealed that, there is a significant impact of learning-through-work on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria. Learning-through-work enhances communications skill; adaptability, flexibility, develops professionally, and collaborate with team member; embrace challenges and opportunities at workplace; and builds strong culture. This finding support the finding of Huang and Yao (2017), who reveal that learning-through-work grow employees skill sets and become valuable assets. The finding is also in support of the view of Nabunya et al. (2019), who argue that learning-through-work helps prepare employees to handle their job effectively, gives opportunities to understand whether employees' chosen career is right. Nyamori (2020) is also of similar view that employees' gain experiences, acquire skills, and develop professionally via learning-through-work.

The test of hypothesis 2, revealed that, there is a significant impact of formal training on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria. Formal training gives high moral and ability to adapt to change; leads to high productivity in an organisation; enhance quick learning; and create better management and improve capital in an organisation. This finding is in agreement with Abdulmalek et al. (2024) who reveal that formal training gives employee capital improvement, moral improvement and ability to adapt to changes. The findings is also in line with Suma and Budi (2021) who said that formal training increases organisation's profitability and employees' effectiveness. it also support the view of Ahmad (2023) is said that formal training enhances employee's personal qualities that increase performance to influences bottom line, saves cost and reduce employee turnover.

The test of hypothesis 3, revealed that, there is a significant impact of feedback on employee effectiveness of Oil Firms in Niger Delta, Nigeria. Feedback gives awareness of what employee is doing; improves performance and organisations' productivity; motivate; and keeps organisation's goal aligned across departments. This finding is in line with the finding of Nabunya et al. (2019).and Alison (2020), who are of similar view that employee gain valuable insights that refine their performance and enhance organisational performance through

feedback. The finding also support the view of Nyamori (2020), who ascertain that feedback enables employees to receive information on their practice, analyze their instructional approaches, and make informed adjustments.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

Management development is the process of developing skills and competencies to perform in management positions which is inevitable for a firm who seek success. Base on the finding of the study, it can be concluded that, management development has a significant relationship with employee effectiveness. Management development enhances communications skill; adaptability, flexibility, develops professionally, and collaborates with team member; embrace challenges and opportunities at workplace; and builds strong culture. It gives high moral and ability to adapt to change; leads to high productivity in an organisation; enhance quick learning; and create better management and improve capital in an organisation. Management development motivates; and keeps organisation's goal aligned across departments. It boasts team performance; enhances communication and collaboration; clarifies goals, roles, and responsibilities; and increases my increase efficacy, efficiency and organisation's productivity. It recognize employees' need; gives support, guidance and continuously improve practice and performance; navigates challenges specific to my job; and refined skills, knowledge and abilities.

Recommendations

- 1 Organizations should ensure the full implementation of developmental programs to promote skills acquisition.
- 2 Organisations should create an environment where learning is as instinctive as breathing, to unlock the full potential of a workforce.
- 3 Managers should institute formal training as basis associated with the use of performance management processes to identify and satisfy developmental needs.

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